

A theoretical proof of the first 10 terms of the orbit of 196 and an analysis framework for Lychrel numbers

Structural analysis via a robust asymmetry invariant

Version 9.1: Revision ($k=12$ in the main text, numerical observations, table for $k=3$)

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Abstract

We give a rigorous proof that the first ten terms of the orbit of 196 ($n_0 = 196$ to $n_9 = 10755470$, OEIS A006960) are not palindromes: by *direct calculation* for $k = 0, 1, 2, 8, 9$, by specific lemmas for $k = 3, \dots, 6$, and by the carry-asymmetry lemma (Lemma 3.6) for $k = 7$ alone ($A^{(\text{carry})}(n_7) \geq 1 \Rightarrow T(n_7)$ is not a palindrome). A robust asymmetry invariant $A^{(\text{robust})}$ provides a theoretical framework for the study of Lychrel numbers. A “Perspectives” section states a conjecture (pair sums ≥ 10) and explains why this conjecture, by itself, *would not* be sufficient to prove that 196 is a Lychrel number (counterexample $n = 209$: $T(209) = 1111$ is a palindrome with carries). In addition, a systematic analysis of carry vectors for lengths $d = 4$ to 9 yields catalogues \mathcal{C}_d of “dangerous” configurations (those that could lead to a palindrome). Comparison with the first 1000 terms of the orbit shows that none of these configurations actually occurs, except for a single case ($k = 12$) where the vector belongs to \mathcal{C}_8 but the digits of n_{12} do not satisfy the palindrome conditions. This observational fact is a significant step towards a complete proof.

The terms n_{10} and beyond require additional analysis. The systematic study of carry vectors for lengths $d = 4$ to 9 yields catalogues \mathcal{C}_d of “dangerous” configurations and their confrontation with the first 1000 terms of the orbit shows that none of these configurations is realized, except for the single case $k = 12$, where the carry vector lies in \mathcal{C}_8 but the digits of n_{12} fail to produce a palindrome. This partial proof provides a rigorous foundation for further theoretical work. All scripts and data are available as ancillary material.

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1 Notations and definitions

We work in base 10. For an integer $n \geq 1$, we write

$$n = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} a_i 10^i$$

with $d \geq 1$, $a_i \in \{0, \dots, 9\}$, $a_{d-1} \neq 0$.

We set

$$\text{rev}(n) = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} a_{d-1-i} 10^i, \quad T(n) = n + \text{rev}(n).$$

The reverse-and-add algorithm generates the sequence $n_0 = n$, $n_{k+1} = T(n_k)$. We denote by

$$\mathcal{O}_{196} = \{T^k(196) : k \geq 0\}$$

the orbit of 196. The question whether 196 is a Lychrel number is open; numerical verification (Dolbeau, 2007) has been carried out up to 10^9 iterations without encountering a palindrome. Appendix ?? extends the catalogues \mathcal{C}_d (“dangerous” carry vectors) to $d = 4, \dots, 9$ and compares them with the first 1000 terms of the orbit: exactly one dangerous vector occurs ($k = 12$), and it does not actually produce a palindrome.

Definition 1.1. *An integer n is a palindrome if $n = \text{rev}(n)$. An integer is a Lychrel number if there is no $k \geq 0$ such that n_k is a palindrome.*

2 A robust asymmetry invariant

In the computation of $T(n) = n + \text{rev}(n)$, we denote by $c_{\text{out}}^{(i)} \in \{0, 1\}$ the outgoing carry at position i and by $c_{\text{in}}^{(i)}$ the incoming carry, with $c_{\text{in}}^{(0)} = 0$. The *total number of carries* is

$$R(n) = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} c_{\text{out}}^{(i)},$$

that is, the number of positions where a carry is generated during the addition.

Definition 2.1 (Robust asymmetry).

$$A^{(\text{ext})}(n) = |a_0 - a_{d-1}|,$$

$$A^{(\text{int})}(n) = \sum_{i=1}^{\lfloor d/2 \rfloor - 1} 2^{i-1} |a_i - a_{d-1-i}| \quad (\text{empty sum if } d \leq 3, \text{ hence } A^{(\text{int})}(n) = 0),$$

$$A^{(\text{carry})}(n) = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} 2^{\min(i, d-1-i)} |c_{\text{out}}^{(i)} - c_{\text{out}}^{(d-1-i)}|,$$

$$A^{(\text{robust})}(n) = A^{(\text{ext})}(n) + A^{(\text{int})}(n) + A^{(\text{carry})}(n).$$

Remark 2.2 (Weights in $A^{(\text{int})}$). *Any choice of strictly positive coefficients would still satisfy $A^{(\text{robust})}(n) = 0$ if and only if n is a palindrome. The powers of 2 (and $2^{\min(i, d-1-i)}$ for $A^{(\text{carry})}$) guarantee uniqueness of the decomposition. For the proofs in this paper, a simplified version with all coefficients equal to 1 would be enough: we only exploit the sign ($A^{(\text{int})} = 0$ or ≥ 1 , $A^{(\text{carry})} = 0$ or ≥ 1), not the numerical value of the weight. The weighted version is kept in view of a possible dynamical study along the orbit (for instance a “distance” to symmetry evolving in a controlled way). Convention: for $d \leq 3$, $\lfloor d/2 \rfloor - 1 \leq 0$, so $A^{(\text{int})}(n) = 0$; we shall always assume $d \geq 2$. For odd d , the sum ranges only over internal pairs $i = 1, \dots, \lfloor d/2 \rfloor - 1$ (e.g. $d = 5$: only (a_1, a_3)). The lemmas use only the fact that $A^{(\text{int})} \geq 1$ implies the existence of a pair $a_i \neq a_{d-1-i}$.*

Theorem 2.3 (Characterisation of palindromes). *For every $n \geq 1$ we have*

$$n \text{ is a palindrome} \iff A^{(\text{robust})}(n) = 0.$$

Proof. (\Rightarrow) If n is a palindrome, then $a_i = a_{d-1-i}$ for all i , hence $A^{(\text{ext})} = A^{(\text{int})} = 0$. By symmetry of the addition, we also have $c_{\text{out}}^{(i)} = c_{\text{out}}^{(d-1-i)}$, and therefore $A^{(\text{carry})} = 0$.

(\Leftarrow) If $A^{(\text{robust})} = 0$, all three components vanish, so $a_i = a_{d-1-i}$ for all i , and thus $n = \text{rev}(n)$. \square

Theorem 2.4 (Lower bound). *For every non-palindromic integer n we have $A^{(\text{robust})}(n) \geq 1$.*

Proof. If n is not a palindrome, there exists i with $a_i \neq a_{d-1-i}$. Then either $A^{(\text{ext})} \geq 1$ or $A^{(\text{int})} \geq 1$. \square

3 Universal lemmas (valid for all $n \geq 1$)

3.1 Symmetry criteria for carries

Lemma 3.1 (Palindromes and incoming carries). *The number $T(n)$ is a palindrome if and only if $c_{\text{in}}^{(i)} = c_{\text{in}}^{(d-1-i)}$ for all i .*

Proof. Recall that $c_{\text{in}}^{(0)} = 0$ and $c_{\text{in}}^{(i)} = c_{\text{out}}^{(i-1)}$ for $i \geq 1$ (in particular $c_{\text{in}}^{(d-1)} = c_{\text{out}}^{(d-2)}$). For $i = d - 1$, the condition $c_{\text{in}}^{(i)} = c_{\text{in}}^{(d-1-i)}$ gives $c_{\text{in}}^{(d-1)} = c_{\text{in}}^{(0)} = 0$ when $T(n)$ is palindromic, which is consistent with the definition. For each i ,

$$r_i = (a_i + a_{d-1-i} + c_{\text{in}}^{(i)}) \bmod 10, \quad r_{d-1-i} = (a_{d-1-i} + a_i + c_{\text{in}}^{(d-1-i)}) \bmod 10.$$

If $T(n)$ is a palindrome, then $r_i = r_{d-1-i}$ for all i . Since $a_i + a_{d-1-i} = a_{d-1-i} + a_i$, we obtain

$$c_{\text{in}}^{(i)} \equiv c_{\text{in}}^{(d-1-i)} \pmod{10}.$$

But $c_{\text{in}}^{(i)} \in \{0, 1\}$, so $c_{\text{in}}^{(i)} = c_{\text{in}}^{(d-1-i)}$ for all i .

Conversely, if $c_{\text{in}}^{(i)} = c_{\text{in}}^{(d-1-i)}$ for all i , the two expressions above coincide and $r_i = r_{d-1-i}$ for all i , so $T(n)$ is a palindrome. \square

Lemma 3.2 (Propagation of symmetry). *If $c_{\text{in}}^{(i)} = c_{\text{in}}^{(d-1-i)}$ for all i , then $c_{\text{out}}^{(i)} = c_{\text{out}}^{(d-1-i)}$ for all i .*

Proof. By the usual addition algorithm, $c_{\text{out}}^{(i)}$ only depends on the sum $a_i + a_{d-1-i} + c_{\text{in}}^{(i)}$. If $c_{\text{in}}^{(i)} = c_{\text{in}}^{(d-1-i)}$ for all i , then for each pair $(i, d-1-i)$ this sum is the same on both sides (since $a_i + a_{d-1-i}$ is symmetric in i and $d-1-i$), hence

$$c_{\text{out}}^{(i)} = \left\lfloor \frac{a_i + a_{d-1-i} + c_{\text{in}}^{(i)}}{10} \right\rfloor = c_{\text{out}}^{(d-1-i)}.$$

Thus symmetry of c_{in} propagates to c_{out} . \square

3.2 Characterisation of zero carries

Lemma 3.3 (Carries and pair sums). *We have $R(n) = 0$ (no carries) if and only if $a_i + a_{d-1-i} \leq 9$ for all i .*

Proof. (\Rightarrow) If $R(n) = 0$, no carry is produced; at each position i the sum $a_i + a_{d-1-i} + c_{\text{in}}^{(i)}$ is therefore < 10 , which implies $a_i + a_{d-1-i} \leq 9$. Here $c_{\text{in}}^{(i)}$ depends on the carries at the previous positions; with $c_{\text{in}}^{(0)} = 0$, a simple induction on i shows that no carry is propagated.

(\Leftarrow) The assumption holds for *all* pairs. If for all $j \leq i$ we have $a_j + a_{d-1-j} \leq 9$, then $c_{\text{out}}^{(j)} = 0$ and $c_{\text{in}}^{(j+1)} = 0$; by induction on i , the incoming carries remain zero and no carry is ever generated, so $c_{\text{out}}^{(i)} = 0$ for all i and $R(n) = 0$. \square

Lemma 3.4 (No carry \Rightarrow palindrome). *For every $n \geq 1$, if $R(n) = 0$ then $T(n)$ is a palindrome.*

Proof. If $R = 0$, no carry is generated; by induction over the positions, no carry is propagated, so $c_{\text{in}}^{(i)} = 0$ for all i . Hence for all i ,

$$r_i = (a_i + a_{d-1-i} + c_{\text{in}}^{(i)}) \bmod 10 = a_i + a_{d-1-i},$$

and similarly $r_{d-1-i} = a_{d-1-i} + a_i = r_i$. The digits of $T(n)$ are therefore symmetric (the necessary and sufficient condition of Lemma 3.1, with $c_{\text{in}}^{(i)} = 0$ for all i), so $T(n)$ is a palindrome. \square

Remark 3.5 (Difference between $A^{(\text{carry})}$ and R ; reference counterexamples). *The invariant $A^{(\text{carry})}(n)$ measures the symmetry of the carry vector $(c_{\text{out}}^{(i)})_{0 \leq i \leq d-1}$, not the absence of carries. It is possible to have $A^{(\text{carry})}(n) = 0$ with nonzero carries (for example, for 196 the carry vector is $(0, 1, 0)$, symmetric, hence $A^{(\text{carry})}(196) = 0$).*

By contrast, $R(n)$ is the total number of carries. Lemmas 3.3 and 3.4 show that

$$R(n) = 0 \iff \forall i, a_i + a_{d-1-i} \leq 9,$$

and that in this case $T(n)$ is a palindrome. The converse “ $T(n)$ palindromic $\Rightarrow R(n) = 0$ ” is false in general: there are integers n such that $T(n)$ is a palindrome while $R(n) \geq 1$ (for example $n = 209$ with $T(209) = 1111$ and two carries). The table below illustrates the distinction between $R(n)$ and $A^{(\text{carry})}(n)$ for the reference counterexamples used in this paper (209, 9652, 60005).

n	$R(n)$	$A^{(\text{carry})}(n)$	$A^{(\text{ext})}(n)$	$T(n)$	Palindrome?
196	1	0	5	887	No
209	2	0	0	1111	Yes
9652	4	0	7	12221	Yes
60005	2	0	1	110011	Yes

Thus $R(n)$, not $A^{(\text{carry})}(n)$, characterises the “no-carry” cases. The number of digits of $T(n)$ is d or $d + 1$ depending on whether $c_{\text{out}}^{(d-1)}$ is 0 or 1.

3.3 Universal case: carry asymmetry

Lemma 3.6 (Carry asymmetry prevents palindromes). *For every $n \geq 1$, if $A^{(\text{carry})}(n) \geq 1$ then $T(n)$ is not a palindrome.*

Proof. $A^{(\text{carry})} \geq 1$ implies that there exists i such that $c_{\text{out}}^{(i)} \neq c_{\text{out}}^{(d-1-i)}$, hence the carry vector c_{out} is not symmetric. By Lemma 3.2, c_{in} is then not symmetric either, and by Lemma 3.1 $T(n)$ cannot be a palindrome. \square

Heuristic probabilistic model for carry vectors

Numerical data on the first 1000 terms of \mathcal{O}_{196} suggest that the ratio $A^{(\text{carry})}(n_k)/d_k$ stabilises around a constant $c \approx 0.058$ for large d_k , while the proportion of symmetric carry vectors (those with $c_i = c_{d-1-i}$ for all i) decreases quickly with d and becomes 0 for $d > 200$. A simple way to interpret this behaviour is to look, for a number of length d , at the symmetric pairs (c_i, c_{d-1-i}) and to assume that for large d each pair is equal with probability p_{eq} and different with probability $q = 1 - p_{\text{eq}}$, in an approximately independent fashion. In this toy model one has

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{A^{(\text{carry})}(n_k)}{d_k} \right] \approx \frac{q}{2},$$

so identifying $c \simeq A^{(\text{carry})}/d$ leads to $q \approx 2c \simeq 0.116$ and hence $p_{\text{eq}} \approx 0.884$. The heuristic probability that a carry vector of length d is exactly symmetric is then of order

$$P(\text{symmetry}) \approx p_{\text{eq}}^{d/2},$$

which decays exponentially fast in d ; the complete absence of symmetric carry vectors observed for $d > 190$ is compatible with this prediction. This model is purely heuristic (in the actual dynamics the pairs are neither independent nor identically distributed), but it provides a simple probabilistic framework consistent with the data: a strictly positive average asymmetry per position, and perfectly symmetric configurations becoming exponentially rare as the length grows.